

level in a field experiment in Tsukuba, Japan, May-Oct 1989. Indica rice varieties IR8, IR24, Milyang 23, Stipepe, Saturn, 68-1, Ch-47, Belle Patna, Guichao 2, and IR2061-214-3 were used. N levels were 0, 35, 70, and 105 kg N as urea/ha. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications, N in the main plots and variety in the subplots. Forty plants/variety were grown in each subplot, at 15- × 25-cm spacing. Quantitative characters were measured on the middle five plants in each subplot. Genetic variance of each character was estimated as

$$Vg = (MSg - MSe)/r$$

where *MSg* and *MSe* are the mean squares for genotype and error, and *r* the number of replications. The relationship of *Vg* and phenotypic mean for each character with N level was determined by correlation analysis (see table).

Correlation coefficients for genetic variance and phenotypic means of 12 characters with N levels.^a

Item	PH	DH	MTN	PN	ETP	TSN
P	-0.982*	-0.788	-0.977*	0.973*	-0.955*	-0.040
G	0.900	-0.957*	0.986*	0.987*	0.649	-0.075
	FSN	FSP	GW	GY	BY	HI
P	-0.895	-0.774	-0.972*	0.961*	0.969*	-0.983*
G	-0.709	0.953*	-0.525	0.888	0.812	-0.378

^aP = correlation coefficient between phenotypic mean and N level, G = correlation coefficient between genetic variance and N level, * = significant at 5% level. PH = plant height, DH = days to heading, MTN = maximum tiller no., PN = panicles/plant, ETP = effective tiller percentage, TSN = total spikelet no., FSN = filled spikelets/panicle, FSP = filled spikelet percentage, GW = 1,000-grain wt, GY = grain yield, BY = biological yield/plant, HI = harvest index.

Genetic responses to N did not always coincide with phenotypic response. The genetic variances of maximum tiller no. (MTN), panicles per plant (PN), and filled spikelets per panicle were positive and significantly correlated with N level. The genetic variance of days to heading (DH) was negative and significantly correlated with N level.

Genetic variation is the basis of rice breeding. It is easier to select for a certain character when its genetic variance is larger. In breeding indica rice, selecting for MTN, PN, and effective tiller percentage would be more efficient at higher N levels. But selecting for DH would be more efficient at lower N levels. ■

Contents of endogenous hormones GA, IAA, and ABA in semidwarf rice

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We measured the level of endogenous GA, IAA, and ABA in near-isogenic lines of indica rices.

Er-Jiu-Qing with *Sd₁* gene, Er-Jiu-Qing with *sd₁* gene, waxy Guang-Lu-Ai 4 with *Wx* gene, and nonwaxy Guang-Lu-Ai 4 with *wx* gene are near-isogenic lines with one gene difference. Four plant types are tall, dwarf a, dwarf b, and superdwarf, japonica type (derived from Jia 23/Xue-He-Ai-Zao (XHAZ) F₃) with *Sd₁Sd₁Sd₃Sd₃*, *sd₁sd₁Sd₃Sd₃*, *Sd₁Sd₁sd₃sd₃*, and *sd₁sd₁sd₃sd₃* genotypes, respectively, by genetic test of plant height and GA, response. Jia 23 (*sd₁* gene) and XHAZ (*sd₃* gene) were the check varieties.

Suge's method of assay and of extraction were used to evaluate hormone level in aboveground plant parts.

Contents of endogenous gibberellin-like substance were higher in tall plants

Table 1. Content of endogenous hormones of near-isogenic lines.^a

Variety	Genotype	Plant height (cm)	Hormone ^a (μg/kg fresh wt)		
			GA	IAA	ABA
Tall Er-Jiu-Qing	<i>Sd₁Sd₁</i>	128.0	1.68 a	0.58 a	0.35 c
Dwarf Er-Jiu-Qing	<i>sd₁sd₁</i>	75.0	1.13 c	0.11 c	0.97 a
Waxy Guang-Lu-Ai 4	<i>WxWx</i>	80.0	1.18 b	0.13 b	0.81 b
Nonwaxy Guang-Lu-Ai 4	<i>wxwx</i>	80.0	1.18 b	0.13 b	0.81 b

^aIn a column, means followed by different letters are significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Table 2. Content of endogenous hormones of near-isogenic plants with different dwarfing genes (μg/kg fresh wt).^a

Plant type	Genotype	Plant height (cm)	Hormone ^a (μg/kg fresh wt)		
			GA	IAA	ABA
Tall	<i>Sd₁Sd₁Sd₃Sd₃</i>	133.5	1.68 a	0.63 a	0.29 d
Dwarf a	<i>sd₁sd₁Sd₃Sd₃</i>	96.0	1.25 d	0.22 b	2.08 c
Dwarf b	<i>Sd₁Sd₁sd₃sd₃</i>	75.0	1.61 bc	0.14 e	2.29 a
Superdwarf	<i>sd₁sd₁sd₃sd₃</i>	45.0	1.57 c	0.09 f	2.32 a
Jia 23 (CK1)	<i>sd₁sd₁Sd₃Sd₃</i>	92.0	1.23 d	0.16 d	2.19 b
Xue-He-Ai-Zao (CK2)	<i>Sd₁Sd₁sd₃sd₃</i>	93.0	1.66 ab	0.19 c	2.16 b

^aIn a column, means followed by different letters are significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

and dwarf type with *sd₃* gene than in dwarf type with *sd₁* gene (Table 1,2). The dwarfs had higher ABA content and significantly lower IAA content than tall plants. *Wx* was not related to

endogenous GA, IAA, and ABA.

We suggest that dwarf plant height was not due to low GA. Low IAA content, however, was the critical factor. ■